

Event Abstract

Injuries in Children, Adolescents and Adults in Amateur Football: An Observational Study

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Background: Football is one of the most popular sports around the world. The benefits of playing it include social, psychological as well as cardiovascular and muscular skeletal benefits. However, as a physical contact sport there are associated injury risks. The aim of this study is to know the injury incidence, type and location in players from an amateur club to design and implement strategies and preventive measures to reduce related collateral effects of football practice.

Methods: A population of 308 federated players was studied, aged between 5 and 29 years old (20 over 19s, 38 under 19s, 38 under 16s, 57 under 14s, 57 under 12s, 44 under 10s and 54 under 8s) distributed over 20 teams. 339 cases of injury occurred during one year.

Results: The most affected population was the over 19s (40.7%) being muscular (52.5%) and ligament (16.5%) levels the most frequent alterations. The most common location was the lower limbs (78.6%) and specifically the thigh (39.8%). Physical load periods (September and February) were highlighted as the months of highest incidence and the average number of visits per injury was 1.34. A statistically significant relationship between hours of training and injuries was noted.

Conclusions: Football is a safe sport to practice at any age because injuries are not normally serious and it is highly recommended given the amount of health benefits obtained.

Keywords: Football, Injuries, Sport.

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